

interstore

D4.2 - Service provision based on connected data spaces report

WP4 - Multiservice and Flexibility Monetisation

T4.2 - Service Provision based on Connected Data Space

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CER	Community Energy Renewable
CYG	CyberGrid
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMS	Energy Management System
ENG	Engineering
ENX	Enel X
EV	Electric Vehicle
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich
GIS	Geographic Information System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HES	HESStec
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IDS	International Data Space
IEEE2030.5	IEEE Standard for Smart Energy Profile Application Protocol
IOT	Internet of Things
LPC	Legacy Protocol Converter
NATS	Neural Autonomic Transport System
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PV	Solar Photovoltaic Panel
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Use Case
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
V2G	Vehicle to Grid
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The task "Service Provision Based on Connected Data Spaces" aims to establish a data-sharing ecosystem that supports the creation of decentralized data models and the deployment of services and functionalities through seamless data exchange. This objective will be achieved by implementing measures to deliver a scalable, open, interoperable, and cyber-secure ICT framework driven by data. The framework will comprehensively support value-added services such as data storage, PV plant and EV charger management, data publishing, advanced search capabilities, and efficient data retrieval within a digital dataspace. The strategy includes the deployment of robust actions to ensure system scalability, openness, interoperability, and cybersecurity—resulting in a resilient ICT infrastructure that enables smooth data flows and enriched service delivery. Ultimately, this will foster innovation, operational efficiency, and sustainable growth in the digital economy.

1 Introduction

The first section provides information on the InterSTORE project consortium, which has worked extensively on utilizing the tools developed in WP2 and collecting data through Service Provisioning based on the Connected Dataspace, the focus of the current T4.2.

1.1 Objectives

This task aims to document the use of a Data-Space Energy Framework and adapt it to the specific case and manage data coming from decentralized management of heterogeneous storage resources, including battery energy storage systems, as well as hybrid energy storage systems.

The objective is to make available a scalable, open, interoperable and cyber-secure ICT data-driven framework that fully supports value-added storage services provision, publishing, search, and retrieval from the common Data Space.

1.2 WP4 AND TASK 4.2 GOALS

By focusing on interoperability, the development of a next-generation energy management system (EMS) that integrates with interoperable Data space and enhances the performance of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) can be a transformative step towards efficient energy use and grid resilience.

The “Service Provision based on Connected Data Space” is a concept that revolves around the integration, exchange, and utilization of data across different systems, organizations, and technologies within a connected ecosystem. The Data Space concept enables efficient data sharing and management while maintaining security, privacy, and interoperability.

1.3 Structure of deliverable

Chapter 1 summarizes the overall objective of task 4.2, followed by goals of the entire WP4 and in deep analysis on T4.2 and relation of WP4 and T4.2

As deliverable D4.2 focuses on Service provision based on connected Data Space; in the Chapter 2 reports an overview of the Energy Data Space Framework developed by ENG, focused on how the tool is composed with reviewing its main functionalities.

Chapter 3 InescTEC identifies the cases in which data is coming from the pilots and used by the partners with complementary data from external sources. By connecting and combining these data types, the dataspace can support advanced analytics, machine learning models, and decision-making systems. The particular case of the Portuguese pilot is highlighted in which a connector as a service was provided with the setup of an intermediate database as a stepping stone to making data from CapWatt’s assets available.

The following chapters are dedicated to the Project’s pilots to describe the data:

Chapter 4 is dedicated to the data coming from the use cases developed in the German pilot. After a brief introduction to the use cases, and the available data, the development steps are presented underlying the internal requirements for safety regulations. Then, the final results are presented underlying the services provided, along with an example of data provided with one of these services.

Chapter 5 Cybergrid has described the Austrian Pilot, the key data gathered from the assets on the field and how the data are exchanged in Data space. In addition, the Use cases data and the concept of decentralized data management with fast external data exchanged was explored through the introduction of open data spaces.

Chapter 6 is dedicated to Enel X Italian Pilot description. It describes the process of implementing the data space connector in a virtual machine outside the Lab network. The data space process development has been reported, the relevant data coming from the Use case implemented and the relative data space services are reported.

Chapter 7, 8 include References and Appendixes (Tables and Figures), respectively. It should be noted that, the Appendix 8.1 (Chapter 8) contains a list of all the services implemented in the Open Data Space.

2 Developments of the Energy Data Space Framework

2.1 Interoperability Framework for InterSTORE – T2.4 Task Overview

The primary goal of Task T2.4 within Work Package 2 (WP2) is to design and implement a robust framework that ensures seamless data interoperability among various stakeholders engaged in InterSTORE processes. This task focuses on leveraging data spaces to enable secure, standardized, and efficient data exchange, building upon the results of other work packages (WPs).

To achieve this, the framework integrates open-source software components, with a strong emphasis on FIWARE-based (a curated framework of Open Source Platform components to accelerate the development of Smart Solutions) [1] technology enablers developed by ENG.A key component is TrueConnector (TRUsted Engineering Connector) [2], which plays a central role in facilitating trusted data exchange within the International Data Space (IDS) ecosystem [3].

2.2 Core Functionalities and Enhancements

The TrueConnector operates through a modular architecture, consisting of:

- An execution core container, responsible for orchestrating secure data exchange mechanisms.
- A data application back-end module, which ensures compliance with the IDS Information Model and enables seamless interaction with external Identity Providers.

For the InterSTORE use case, the framework is extended and enhanced to enable applications to generate, consume, and manage data efficiently while ensuring interoperability within the IDS framework.

2.3 Key Research and Implementation Areas

Beyond the core functionalities, Task T2.4 explores and integrates additional technologies to strengthen the Interoperable Energy Data Space Framework, including:

- User-Friendly Open-Source GUI – A graphical interface designed to simplify the utilization of the Energy Data Space Framework and centralized services, improving accessibility for end users.
- Blockchain and Smart Contracts – Implemented to certify and validate transactions involving data exchange among multiple participants, ensuring data integrity, transparency, and trust in the system.
- Push Mechanism Implementation – Enabling data providers to upload data synchronously to (external) services, ensuring real-time or event-driven data updates.
- IEEE 2030.5 [4] Integration via NATS Protocol [5] – Supporting the integration of energy data exchange standards, improving compatibility with smart grid and energy management systems.

The following figure (Figure 1) shows a block diagram of the latest version of the Energy Data Space Framework released in the Interstore project.

Figure 1. Energy Data Space Connector Architecture

For more detailed information on this topic, please refer to Deliverable D2.8, which was submitted in March 2024 (M27). This document provides an in-depth analysis of the implemented features, technical specifications, and key findings related to the Energy Data Space Framework within the project.

2.4 Expected Outcomes and Deployment

The final deliverable of Task T2.4 is the Interoperable Data Space Framework, a comprehensive suite of interoperability services designed for deployment in both local and cloud environments. The framework supports multiple deployment models, including centralized, distributed, and federated approaches, ensuring flexibility based on project needs.

Moreover, these interoperability services are designed to seamlessly integrate with assets from other work packages, allowing project pilots to incorporate them directly into their data collection and management pipelines.

Appendix 8.1, included in Chapter 8, provides a comprehensive list of all the services that have been implemented within the Open Data Space.

2.5 Impact on Task T4.2

This work is of critical importance as it lays the foundation for ensuring data interoperability and seamless integration within the InterSTORE ecosystem. The Interoperable Data Space Framework, developed in Task T2.4 will be directly implemented to support the correct execution and functionality of Task T4.2, ensuring that all processes and offered services align with the project interoperability, security, and efficiency goals.

The Energy Data Space Framework will provide pilots with the necessary tools and methodologies to define the specific energy offered services required for their operations. It will also facilitate the secure and efficient sharing of interoperability data, ensuring compliance with standardized protocols and enabling seamless data exchange among different partner and stakeholders within the ecosystem.

3 Data service valorization and federated data sharing (InescTEC)

Within the context of providing data to the InterSTORE dataspace, several sources of data were used. These can be grouped in two categories: Pilot data and complementary data from external sources.

For the purpose of exploring the valorization cases further described in D4.3, the pilots created dedicated services in which they set out to share the generated data from their assets' operation. These are mostly data from PV generation, Battery operation and EV chargers. InescTEC also created services providing every day, CO₂ data being updated daily for every pilot location, Day-ahead prices for every pilot location and weather forecast data. Each pilot deployed its version of the InterSTORE Connector, all users of the dataspace middleware created by Engineering partner. In the case of InescTEC it made available its connector as a service to CapWatt, so that they could share the operational data from their assets.

Four valorization cases were created. These were:

- PV performance evaluation – Compare the generated PV energy from similar installations to evaluate performance. The PV GIS was used as a base for comparison, but can be particularly useful in a renewable energy community environment for example.
- Green charging EV ranking – A gamification approach between partners that can be an incentive for companies to pursue charging sessions in the least carbon intensive hours from the grid
- HESS optimal dispatch making use of data available in the dataspace such as emissions and day-ahead prices, partners can automatically consume this data to dispatch their battery systems.
- Anomaly detection algorithm, with which partners could use trained data of similar technologies and have a benchmark of the threshold to apply to their systems
- A supplementary case is more business oriented, in which flexibility availability sharing from CapWatt's battery system is provided every day to an aggregation-connected platform via dataspace service.

Besides the data from the assets themselves from the Portuguese pilot, InescTEC is also sharing data from a federated platform SENTINEL [6] in order to complement the existing datasets, enabling thus the valorization cases to be run. In order to prepare data and to make it available to be shared in the InterSTORE dataspace, InescTEC set up a database with dedicated folders.

This database was designed to securely store and share various energy-related datasets within a multi-tenant environment. It was built using Laravel (with the help of QuickAdminPanel), it offers both a web interface and REST API for data access and management. A key priority is data protection, achieved through UUID-based file identification and Laravel Sanctum-based authentication. By combining a user-friendly dashboard with robust security features, the platform ensures controlled, efficient data exchanges.

Folders Created and Data Uploaded to the Data Space:

- CO₂ Carbon-Intensity by Country (Electricity_Maps)
Source: Electricity_Maps

- Data: Carbon intensity metrics per country, supporting analyses of environmental impacts in energy consumption.
- Battery System Operation Data (Baterias 4A)
Source: Capwatt
Data: Operational logs for battery systems, useful for monitoring performance and optimizing battery dispatch.
- Hybrid Dispatch
Source: Inesctec
Data: Control and dispatch schedules for hybrid energy systems, helping to coordinate generation resources.
- PV Generation Data (Consumo e Produção 4A)
Source: Capwatt
Data: Photovoltaic production and consumption records, aiding in solar resource planning and performance tracking.
- EV Chargers Sessions (EVIO)
Source: Capwatt
Data: Electric Vehicle charging session details, vital for load forecasting and charger infrastructure management.
- Day-Ahead Electricity Prices (ENTSO-E)
Source: ENTSO-E
Data: Forecasted electricity prices, critical for scheduling and cost-optimization in energy trading.
- Weather Data by Country
Source: Sentinel / MeteoGalicia
Data: Meteorological forecasts and observations linked to energy production and consumption patterns.
- Flexibility
Source: Inesctec
Data: Records of flexible generation and load resources, allowing for demand response and grid balancing strategies.

Below, the Figure 2 below shows a print screen of the database environment, with some folders created for each service and another print screen with an example of files in one of the folders, structured by date and service name.

Figure 2. Folders created in the database as an interface to the dataspace

In [Figure 3](#), yet another screenshot of the files inside an example folder (PV generation), in which all files are placed with a daily frequency. These files are then pushed to the connector.

Figure 3. Examples of files in one of the folders

A back-end code in python was developed to screen the database for new files at 20h daily, and every time a new file was found, it was “uploaded” to the corresponding data-space service. Further features of the database, justifying the choice for this option are:

- **Multi-Tenancy System**

Each user operates within a dedicated and secure space, ensuring complete isolation from other users. Access is restricted to their personal dashboard, where they can view and manage only their own files. Administrators have full access to monitor and manage all user entries across the system, including the ability to assign roles, set permissions, and oversee content to ensure proper system governance. Users function within siloed environments, where database queries are automatically scoped to their respective accounts, preventing unauthorized access to other users' data.

- **Secure File Access with UUIDs**

Assigning Universally Unique Identifiers (UUIDs) instead of predictable file paths enhances security by obfuscating URLs, making unauthorized access nearly impossible. Secure, direct links allow users to access their files without exposing actual server paths, preventing unauthorized entry and ensuring data integrity.

Files are addressed using version 4 UUIDs (e.g., <https://10.61.6.197:8001/download/58e4f9da-9d4c-4a3d-bdc6-315f560c2aa8>) instead of incremental IDs, reducing the risk of unauthorized access. Security measures include auth middleware, which restricts access to authenticated users, and signed middleware, which validates time-limited download URLs, ensuring controlled and secure file access.

- **Storage & Upload System**

Supporting local, S3, and SFTP storage, Laravel’s Filesystem API ensures flexible and scalable file management. Files are stored efficiently across different storage options, allowing seamless integration with cloud services and local disks. Configuration settings in `config/filesystems.php` define storage parameters, optimizing performance and accessibility.

Client-side validation enforces file type and size restrictions before upload, preventing incompatible or oversized files from being processed. This approach enhances user experience by minimizing upload errors and ensuring compliance with system storage policies.

- **Admin Dashboard (QuickAdminPanel)**

QuickAdminPanel automates CRUD operations by generating Blade templates and controllers for essential system management functions. User accounts can be created or disabled, file analytics provide insights into storage usage and upload trends, and role-based permission matrices define access levels across the platform.

Three primary user roles structure the system. Administrators have full control, allowing them to modify user roles and conduct file audits. Simple users receive basic access, while premium users benefit from extended storage quotas with certain limitations.

CRUD operations include a role creation button, edit and delete actions, a paginated list displaying 100 entries per page, and a search function for efficiently managing roles. These features streamline administrative tasks, ensuring efficient user and data management.

By categorizing datasets into dedicated folders and securing access via UUIDs and role-based permissions, this platform offered a streamlined approach for exchanging and managing critical energy information—such as CO₂ intensity, battery operations, hybrid dispatch, PV generation, EV charging, electricity prices, and weather data. QuickAdminPanel simplifies administrative tasks, while Laravel's API capabilities enable programmatic interactions for automated data flows. Overall, it provides a user-centric, secure, and scalable Data Space for modern energy and flexibility management needs.

4 DER operational data service provision to Data Space (JULICH)

The Living Lab Energy Campus (LLEC) at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ, “Jülich Re-search Centre”) constitutes a testbed where both innovative hardware and software solutions for district energy systems are tested under close to real conditions, in a scientifically monitored environment incorporating real users. The basis for LLEC is formed by the already existing infrastructure of the FZJ, which is one of the largest interdisciplinary re-search centers in Europe. In this framework, a FIWARE-based ICT platform is deployed to gather data from the assets on the field and provide setpoints for their operation.

This lead to a centralised data management system, self-maintained and fully deployed on premises and with no access for external users. Thanks to the deployment of dataspaces in the framework of the InterSTORE project, data can be safely exchanged with external users.

A simplified scheme of the overall architecture is provided in the figure below.

Figure 4. Simplified schematics of data path from origin to open data spaces

4.1 UCs Brief Description and Relevant Data

In InterSTORE Forschungszentrum Jülich’s (FZJ) demonstration activities take place in the campus of the research center, which constitutes the German pilot site. In particular, two use cases are considered:

- UC3 – Grid supporting BESS.
- UC8 – Multiphysics flexibility optimization for Home Management Systems and their global integration.

Both use cases strongly rely on data exchange between the assets on the field and the energy management algorithm running on the campus Information and communication technology (ICT) platform. Thanks to the inclusion of the open data space connector, such data can be also exchanged with external, verified, subscribers. Among others, key information which might be relevant for the users, and thus are provided via the data space connector are:

- Power generated by the large photovoltaic field (1.1 MWp)
- Power flows (charge/discharge) and state of charge associated with the usage of the Riello high-power battery system.

- Power flows (charge/discharge) and state of charge associated with the usage of the Tesla high-energy battery system.

4.2 Connection to the open data space

The connection to open data spaces enables new possibilities for data sharing at FZJ, which were not foreseen so far. In particular, due to internal security policies, data has been always stored in local, self-managed databases, preventing access to external users. In order to establish the connection to open data spaces, a public IP address has been released, and the FZJ services have been exposed via the URL: <https://fzj-interstore.fz-juelich.de>. The deployment process was not trivial, and the faced challenges are reported below.

4.2.1 Development steps

In order to expose an IP address outside the FZJ network, discussions have been carried out with the operators of the FZJ communication network. To limit cybersecurity risks, it has been decided to expose only a limited number of ports associated with the public IP address. These ports, corresponds to the ports that are needed to successfully deploy the open data spaces connection. In addition, to allow the exchange with some specific external services, additional access has been granted to such services, like <https://cc-cpes-248.ines-ctec.pt:8889/data> for connections with InescTEC.

To remain in compliance with security requirements at FZJ, the system hosting the FZJ services has been deployed on a "DMZ", i.e. "demilitarised zone", which protects the service's internal local area network (LAN) from untrusted data traffic.

Thus, the Docker container of the open data spaces has been deployed on a dedicated workstation running Ubuntu Linux operating system (OS). This solution was chosen due to the fact that Linux-based OS supports Docker features natively. Because of this, the containers can run directly on the host OS, leading to faster startups and low resource usage.

To properly link the public IP address to the data space connector, another docker container has been deployed in parallel, to use HAproxy as a proxy.

4.2.2 Final Results

Now that the data space connector has been deployed, it can be safely used by FZJ authorized users to provide and consume data. As an example, the following screenshot of Figure 5 shows the dashboard of the FZJ connector, with consumed data entities, data provided, offered services and subscriptions to external services.

Figure 5. UI of Open data spaces operated in FZJ environment

4.3 Data Availability via Data Spaces

As mentioned above, at FZJ, two use cases are considered for the demonstration, UC3 and UC8. In both use cases, the focus is on the optimization of energy storage systems operation to provide grid supporting services and promote self-consumption from renewable resources. Thus, it has been decided to make use of the data spaces to share with external partners the data associated with the operations of the two battery systems and the power generated by the large PV field installed on campus.

Consequently, 3 services have been created for data provision, plus one for debugging purposes. An overview of such services is shown in the figure below, with a screenshot of the data space connector interface used at FZJ.

Figure 6. Services offered with the data space connector at FZJ

While service with #1 is meant to be used for internal debugging purposes, the data provided via services with #2-4 can be used by any subscribed user. For example, in the figures below, it is shown the structure of the service #2, “PV Generation Data”, and an example of the data provided via this service, already available to subscribed users.

Figure 7. Example of the PV Generation Data service provided by FZJ

#	Category	Title	Created On	Description
1	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - Dec 2024	06/03/2025 11:35	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during Dec 2024.
2	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - Nov 2024	06/03/2025 11:34	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during Nov 2024.
3	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - Oct 2024	06/03/2025 11:26	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during Oct 2024.
4	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - Sept 2024	06/03/2025 11:23	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during Sept 2024.
5	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - August 2024	06/03/2025 11:23	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during August 2024.
6	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - July 2024	06/03/2025 11:22	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during July 2024.
7	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - June 2024	06/03/2025 11:22	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during June 2024.
8	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - May 2024	06/03/2025 11:21	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during May 2024.
9	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - April 2024	06/03/2025 11:20	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during April 2024.
10	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - March 2024	06/03/2025 11:11	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during March 2024.
11	02 - Measurements and Monitoring	InterSTORE - FZJ PV Generation - Feb 2024	06/03/2025 11:11	Data generated from PV field installed at FZJ during Feb 2024.

Figure 8. Example of the data provided via the PV Generation Data service at FZJ

In particular, PV generation data are provided on a monthly basis, with a time resolution of 5 minutes. To ensure that users can make meaningful usage of such data, the following quantities, monitored at the point of common coupling (PCC) where the PV field is connected to the FZJ network, have been made available:

- Timestamp (referred to UTC)
- Network frequency [Hz]
- Line-to-neutral Voltage RMS [V] (phase 1, phase 2, phase 3 and neutral)
- Line Current RMS [A] (phase 1, phase 2, phase 3 and neutral)
- Active power at PCC [W] (phase 1, phase 2, and phase 3)
- Reactive power at PCC [var] (phase 1, phase 2, and phase 3)
- Apparent power at PCC [VA] (phase 1, phase 2, and phase 3)

This information can be used, for example, in association with the weather information provided by InescTEC via their Weather Forecast Data service, to perform analysis on the efficiency of the PV field installed at FZJ.

A detailed overview of all services implemented in the Open Data Space can be found in Appendix 8.1, located in Chapter 8.

5 DSO flexibility service provision to Data Space (CyberGrid)

CyberGrid has more than 15 years of experience providing flexibility on energy markets. With such extensive knowledge in balancing and wholesale markets it came to the conclusion that data exchange, its storage, traceability and ways to analyze it are the foundation towards optimization of bidding and maximization of market revenues. The same conclusion can be found also in some research literature (Laitila Miikka, 2017, [Data monetization: Utilizing data as an asset to generate new revenues for firms](#))(Tobias Enders, Ronny Schüritz, Wiebke Frey, 2019, [Capturing Value from Data: Exploring Factors Influencing Revenue Model Design for Data-Driven Services](#)). Moreover a similar research explored and compared centralised and decentralised data approaches and its effects on day to day business (Sujit Wings, Janne Harkonen, 2022, [Decentralised or centralised management of data and products: influence on revenue-generating processes](#)). The centralized data management has been pursued by CyberGrid for its entire history but for the purposes of InterSTORE the decentralized data management with fast external data exchanged was explored with introduction of open data spaces. An example of data path from origin to open data spaces is presented within a Simplified schematics shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Simplified schematics of data path from origin to open data spaces

5.1 UCs Brief Description and Relevant Data Availability

In InterSTORE CyberGrid's research and development in general revolves heavily around its Austrian pilot - Energy community Dietach. In the pilot CyberGrid leads two use cases:

- UC1 – DES Flexibility Market Monetisation, focuses on enabling monetisation of Distributed Energy Resource (DER) flexibility at various markets.
- UC2 – Energy community DES utilisation, is all about enhancing community self-sufficiency mode in order to minimise their reliance on the grid and in turn help the overburdened grid and energy community members to reduce costs.

Both use cases have a common threat of making optimal operational decisions based on gathered data and based on this, they can participate in various energy markets. With this in mind it is logical that open data spaces and data exchange would revolve around data gathered and optimization processes in the pilot itself and/or on the energy markets. CyberGrid thought of generating DSO system offers that could be shared to parties through this new approach. Basics of the task:

- We bid available flexibility on TSO market first or wholesale market (business as usual).
- Remaining amount of flexibility will be calculated and offered to DSO as a service.
- DSO market will be simulated for the purpose of this project.
- The service will be offered on distributed-data-sharing-platform called Open Data Spaces.
- The idea of such services is that whoever would subscribe or “listen” to this channel can request our provided service.

A schematic step-by-step diagram can be found on the figure below:

Figure 10. Presentation of action flow in Austrian pilot

5.2 Connecting to the open data space

Connection to open data spaces is in essence a complete turnabout in CyberGrid company rules on how data is treated. Until now the major focus of CyberNoc was to store data as secure as possible with limiting options to share it due to security risks it might bare. What is more, its infrastructure was not designed to be exposed to internet and publicly visible. This all changed with the decision of CyberGrid to open outwards via open data spaces. Regardless of the decision, the software was not yet ready for such change and the steps taken were met with many challenges.

5.2.1 Development steps

Primary task of CyberNoc integration with open data space connector is to understand the provided open source code ([Horizont-Europe-Interstore, Data-Space-Connector](#)) and decide

on best approach of communication between the two. It was decided that a connector inside the existing CyberNoc infrastructure is the simplest and cleanest solution towards sharing the data. In addition, this approach maximizes the security for energy community member's data, as it is not exposed to any additional risk. As CyberNoc and all its belonging tools are stored in AWS cloud and run by [Kubernetes](#), integration was not simple due to the fact that open data spaces main deployment strategy is in virtual machine (VM) as a docker container.

5.2.1.1 Docker vs Kubernetes

Difference in primary integration approaches made work harder for CyberGrid's Information Technology (IT) team who needed to understand open data space's docker in detail in order to troubleshoot all the gaps that Kubernetes did not find by itself. This was particular obvious when parallel service tried to communicate to open data service. For example, when energy community tool and market arbitrage tool maximized the value of produced energy, they compiled data of what energy is left and tried to push it to docker service on daily basis. The open data space however were not prepared to communicate with such services and needed some additional work.

5.2.1.2 Outward connection

After successful implementation and coordination with other services in CyberGrid's AWS environment the connector was enabled to connect outwards. This step was done with delicacy in order to keep the security as high as possible. In coordination with outward connection a dedicated service was created in the UI part of the connector. From this platform the permissions to access the data are also given to all trustworthy and interested partners.

5.2.2 Final result

At the end of deployment process and considering all the issues open data space connector can be operated by internal CyberGrid employees (VPN is needed) and accessed through AWS account of the company. On the below picture you can observe connector and offered DSO service

Figure 11. UI of Open data spaces operated in CyberGrid environment

Consequently a service called DSO Flexibility Energy Offer has been created and offered on the platform. An overview of it is shown on the Figure 12 below.

Figure 12 DSO Flexibility Energy Offer service offered on the platform.

Data provided until now to said service can be observed on Figure 13. The list is short as device preparation in the pilot, which is the basis for creating the offer, is not yet fully operational.

Figure 13. Data provided to DSO flexibility Energy offer.

Meanwhile CyberGrid collects flexibility offers from other project partners through the connector (via push mechanism). The presentation of received data can be seen on Figure 14, while the details of an exchange on Figure 15.

Figure 14 Data exchange timeline of push mechanism of CyberGrid.

Figure 15. Example of the data provided by partners as a flexibility offer to CyberGrid.

5.3 Focus on the development process and new functionalities

CyberGrid developed the new approach to be able to participate on DSO balancing markets by providing available energy or ability to consume energy for congestion management on the local network.

5.3.1 Preconditions

CyberGrid gathers data of all assets of all energy community members participating in InterSTORE. From there the designated process optimizes behavior of batteries and assets in general based on the forecasted energy production. After the internal optimization excess energy is bidded on energy markets (more on this you can read in section 5.1 or in D4.1. - New generation EMS for HEMS, HESS and flexibility management report). Afterwards the remaining energy is bundled and forwarded to open data space connector where it is published for each day.

5.3.2 Data governance

As mentioned already data security has always been the priority of CyberGrid. This is true even more in this use case where we are working with data of households and their assets. In order to keep consistency and our integrity about good approaches of data governance the gathered data will be aggregated on energy community level for each time interval. Moreover, each member participating in the project will have access to CyberNoc UI to check his incoming data but will not be able to check the data of other members.

More details on data governance in Austrian pilot can be found in D5.1 (https://interstore-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/Attachment_0.pdf).

6 EV and other operational data service provision to Data Space (Enel X)

The Use Case 9 identifies and analyses how different type of storage technologies (Storage Industrial, Residential, Commercial&Industrial, PV and EVs chargers) can contribute in a unique cluster to provide flexibility and grid services.

Analyzing the data process tested in the UC9 (Figure 16), implementing a flexibility service requires the collection and management of a series of relevant data to optimize energy demand based on grid conditions, energy availability, telemetries from the asset and service performance.

Figure 16. Architecture of UC9

6.1 UC Brief Description and Relevant Data Availability

The connection to open data spaces enables new possibilities for data sharing at Enel X which were not foreseen so far.

In particular, due to internal security policies, data has been always stored in local DB, self-managed databases, preventing access to external users.

In order to establish the connection to open data spaces, a public IP address has been released, and the Enel X services have been exposed via the URL: ecc-provider:8889/data

The use case uses distributed energy resources (DERs); they provide telemetry to energy management systems to be processed and used in flexibility services to be sold on the energy markets. In the pilot Enel X leads use cases regarding network flexibility services for :

Relevant data available shown in the following Table 1:

#	Living lab	Info available from T5.1	ENX
1	UC9 : Brief Description and relevant data available	Simulation of DSO order to be executed by an aggregated DER: EVs, Storage res, Storage commercial and industrial and utility scale storage. In addition, use cases will be simulated in order to manage residential, industrial and Evs customers.	Power data from PV, Storage, EVs chargers
2	Who is data provider and who is data consumer	data Provider	Data coming from asset will be shared in dataspace to be analyzed by partners in order to calculate KPI and implement flex service

3	Which data will be provided (data Typology)	CSV	timestamp, voltage ,current, battery status (e.g. SoC, power injected/absorbed), PV power generation
4	Data frequency-format - volume	From 1 minute to 15-minute time step	frequency can vary (from 1 to 15 min). Format will be csv. Dimension file 1 week data are about 1MB
5	Service and Macro-service category		DSO ancillary service, balancing order
6	Which data will be consumed	PV, EV chargers, Battery datasets,	telemetries from DERs
7	Which service the data is used for? Which category of service is?	Data are used to feed algorithm	Battery optimization, EV chargers ranking, PV performance evaluation, Flexibility availability provision and computation
8	With which frequency will be uploaded the data?	once per month	monthly
9	Which are the assets from where the information will be collected?	PVs, Storages and EVs	PV, Storages, EV
10	From when and up to when data will be provided	january25	starting from test on (2025)

Table 1. Relevant data in Dataspace

Below (Figure 13) is reported an example of Data Entity providing as EV charger V2G asset.

The screenshot displays the 'Energy Data Space Connector' web application. The browser address bar shows the URL: localhost:8080/editDataEntity?id=718e4412-fa56-442c-8d34-17cd242c8253. The application interface features a dark sidebar on the left with navigation links: Home, Dashboard, Services, Data exchange, and Connector settings. The main content area is titled 'Data Entity' and 'View Data'. It is divided into two main sections:

- Basic information:** This section contains four input fields:
 - ID:** 718e4412-fa56-442c-8d34-17cd242c8253
 - Title:** dati EV CHARGERS V2g
 - Description:** dati telemetrie ev scarica
 - File:** scarica_v2g.xlsx
- Assigned To Data Offering:** This section contains four input fields:
 - Data Offering:** 63ebe062-2ce3-484d-800e-b394a736e21e
 - Title:** flex service test
 - Profile Format:** (empty field)
 - Profile Description:** (empty field)

The footer of the application shows the year 2025, the Eng logo, and the version number 1.0.6.

Figure 17. EV Chargers V2g data entity

6.2 Connection to the open data space

The Interoperable Data Space Framework is a robust solution for facilitating seamless data exchange across various environments. The fact that the interoperability services can integrate with assets means that different parts of a project can easily share data and insights. This is especially important in complex, multi-phase projects where different teams or stakeholders might have specialized EMS platforms. Project pilots can streamline the process of gathering, analyzing, and storing data. This improves efficiency and ensures consistency in data handling across various systems and environments.

Primary tasks of integrating open data spaces into Enel X infrastructure is to understand the provided open source code ([Horizont-Europe-Interstore, Data-Space-Connector](#)) and decide on best approach of integrating into Enel X infrastructure.

The centralized data management approach has been the traditional model; however, with InterSTORE, the focus of this task is to explore the decentralized data management and the value generated by exchanging data in a common data space framework, which emphasizes faster external data exchange and the introduction of open data spaces.

6.2.1 Development steps

A virtual machine, with the following characteristics, has been prepared in AWS data servers to host data space environment; since the service will be exposed to the internet, it was created in the DMZ network behind WAF (Web Firewall Application).

The deployment process involves the use of Docker containers. The use of Docker guarantees not only an easy deployment process and total portability of the solution, but also a high level of scalability of the released applications. The hardware and operating system prerequisites are:

- A 64bit 2-core processor
- 8GB RAM Memory
- 50GB of disk space or more

The software prerequisites include:

- Linux or Windows (preferably Server edition) Operative System (OS);
- docker and docker-compose;

Energy Data Space Connector software and its components will be delivered utilizing the Docker containers functionalities. Firstly, the Docker platform has to be downloaded and installed accordingly to the OS of the server to host the deployment. For the correct installation of docker and docker-compose, please refer to the official guides: <https://docs.docker.com/get-docker/>

Installation software:

Data space framework : <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Data-Space-Connector>

Site access: <http://hlaawzin9f00.dmzmi.enel:8080/login> (see Figure 14)

Access to the server:

Figure 18. Access screen to Dataspace framework

Figure 19. ENX Local access to Dataspace connector and settings

In the Figure 15 is reported the user information using local access through the Local connector.

In a common data space, the combination of network flexibility, services, and the monetization/valorization of data enables the creation of a thriving, collaborative environment. This system helps participants leverage data to unlock new business models, enhance their services, and ultimately generate value from the shared ecosystem.

6.3 Final Result

Now that the data space connector has been deployed, it can be safely used by ENX authorized users to provide and consume data.

As an example, the picture below shows the dashboard of the ENX connector, with consumed data entities, data provided, offered services and subscriptions to external services.

Below (Figure 16) is reported the sharing data workflow:

Figure 20. ENX Data Space Dashboard

Thus, it has been decided to make use of the data spaces to share with external partners the data associated with the operations of the battery systems and the power generated by the PVs field installed in the Lab and the EVs chargers allocated to Interstore project. The data are collected from the SCADA with 15' frequency and loaded on Dataspace monthly.

Figure 21. ENX Data provided

The data provided via services can be used by any subscribed user. For example, in the figures below, it is shown the structure of the service #-4, Storage power, PV generation power, EVs exchange.

Home

My Offered Services New +

Navigate to your Offered Services

Service status: any -

Offered Services Categorization

Navigate & Filter Data Offerings by Category, Service, Business Object & User categorization tree

- + 02 - Measurements and Monitoring
- + 03 - Forecasts

Filters

Select & Refine Search

QCategories

QCross platform services

QBusinnes object

#		Category	Title	Created On	Profile Format	Profile Description	Status	Subscriptions
				Filter	Filter	Filter		
1		Measurements and Monitoring Resource information DER structural Data	flex service test	05/11/2024 16:53			active	INESC inesc1 ENX e Carbone Lor...
2		Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	Storage power exchange data	25/06/2024 13:10	Csv	To provide data about storage power exchange in X Lab Rome	active	ENX enx2 FZJ fzj1 INESC inesc1
3		Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	EV power exchange data	25/06/2024 13:09	Csv	To provide data about EV power exchange in X Lab Rome	active	FZJ fzj1 INESC inesc1
4		Measurements and Monitoring Metering data Flexible Resource Metering data	PV generation data	25/06/2024 13:07	Csv	To provide data about PV generation in X Lab Rome	active	FZJ fzj1 INESC inesc1
5		Forecasts Dynamic line rating (Flexibility) Resources	Prova	05/06/2024 14:53			active	INESC inesc1 ENX enx2 ENX enx2

Figure 22. ENX Offered Services

For a complete listing of the services implemented in the Open Data Space, refer to Appendix 8.1 in Chapter 8.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable, D4.2 - Service Provision Based on Connected Data Spaces based on work carried out in task T4.2, has outlined the key developments and implementations related to the Energy Dataspace Framework and its role in enabling federated data sharing and service provision across multiple project pilots and partners.

Throughout the document, we have detailed the advancements in the Energy Dataspace Framework, emphasizing its capacity to facilitate secure, interoperable, and efficient data exchange among participants. The integration of data valorization mechanisms has been explored, particularly in the context of INESC TEC / CAPWATT, where federated data sharing has been leveraged to optimize energy services and enhance decision-making processes.

Further implementations have been analyzed across different pilots:

- JÜLICH has demonstrated service provision within the Energy Dataspace, highlighting how its infrastructure enables effective data exchange and collaboration.
- CyberGrid has focused on the integration of its platform within the connected dataspace, showcasing real-world applications of data-driven energy services.
- Enel X has contributed to the enhancement of data service provision by leveraging connected data spaces to support innovative energy solutions and grid optimization strategies.

The insights and developments presented in this deliverable highlight the transformative potential of connected data spaces in the energy sector. By enabling secure data exchange, seamless interoperability, and service innovation, this work lays the foundation for more efficient, transparent, and scalable energy management solutions across the ecosystem. The additional efforts dedicated in WP5 will further refine and expand these implementations, ensuring the full realization of the Energy Dataspace Framework within pilot energy demonstration applications.

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9 APPENDIXES

9.1 List of provisioned Services in Interstore Energy Data Space Connector

The following table shows the services registered within the Energy Data Space Connector.

Offered Service	Creation Date	Offering Type	Offering Company	BO Name	Macro Service Name	Category Name
Flexibility & Availability offers	22/01/2025 11:34	push	CYG	(Flexibility) Resources	Dynamic line rating	Forecasts
Test Push service	11/12/2024 20:14	push	ENG	Grid available flexibility (electricity & heating)	Generic-User defined service	Generic- User defined service
flex service test	05/11/2024 16:53	data	ENX	DER structural Data	Resource information	Measurements and Monitoring
TEST Service FZJ	09/10/2024 13:23	data	FZJ	Generic	Generic-User defined service	Generic- User defined service
introduction data	16/09/2024 13:10	data	CYG	Grid available flexibility (electricity & heating)	Generic-User defined service	Generic- User defined service
DSO Flexibility Energy Offer	31/07/2024 10:14	data	CYG	Grid available flexibility (electricity & heating)	Generic-User defined service	Generic- User defined service
PV Generation Data	10/07/2024 9:53	data	FZJ	Meter Data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
Tesla Battery System Operation Data	10/07/2024 9:52	data	FZJ	Flexible Resource Metering data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
Riello Battery System Operation Data	10/07/2024 9:46	data	FZJ	Flexible Resource Metering data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
Storage power exchange data	25/06/2024 13:10	data	ENX	Flexible Resource Metering data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
EV power exchange data	25/06/2024 13:09	data	ENX	Flexible Resource Metering data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
PV generation data	25/06/2024 13:07	data	ENX	Flexible Resource Metering data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring

Day-ahead Prices per Pilot Zone	25/06/2024 11:00	data	INESC	Energy clearing results	Market information	Market
Battery System Operation Data	25/06/2024 10:59	data	INESC	Flexible Resource Metering data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
EV Chargers Sessions Data	25/06/2024 10:58	data	INESC	Meter Data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
PV Generation Data	25/06/2024 10:55	data	INESC	Meter Data	Metering data	Measurements and Monitoring
CO2 Day-ahead emissions data from pilot sites	25/06/2024 10:51	data	INESC	Forecast data (load, generation, FSP)	Forecast data (general)	Forecasts
Weather Forecast Data	25/06/2024 10:45	data	INESC	weather forecast	Forecast data (general)	Forecasts
TestService	19/06/2024 10:50	data	ENG	Electric Grid Aggregated Flexibility for Congestion Management	Generic-User defined service	Generic- User defined service
INESC TEC Test Service	13/06/2024 13:51	data	INESC	Generic	Generic-User defined service	Generic- User defined service
First service	24/05/2024 16:50	data	ENG	(Flexibility) Resources	Dynamic line rating	Forecasts

Table 2. Offered Services in Energy Data Space Connector

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